

Supplementary material

Suppl Table 1 Determinants of the BALP/iPTH-ratio in Japanese and Belgian patients receiving hemodialysis

	Belgian cohort			Japanese cohort		
	Lowest (<i>n</i> = 59)	Middle (<i>n</i> = 59)	Highest (<i>n</i> = 61)	Lowest (<i>n</i> = 61)	Middle (<i>n</i> = 64)	Highest (<i>n</i> = 62)
BALP/iPTH ratio	0.05 [0.04; 0.06]	0.10 [0.08; 0.11]	0.25 [0.17; 0.36] †	0.05 [0.04; 0.07]	0.11 [0.09; 0.14]	0.23 [0.19; 0.30] †
Age, years	59 ± 11	61 ± 11	58 ± 12	57 ± 12	62 ± 10	58 ± 12 †
Sex, male, %	47 (79.7%)	38 (64.4%)	34 (55.7%) †	47 (77.0%)	45 (70.3%)	33 (53.2%) †
Diabetes, %	17 (28.8%)	25 (42.4%)	19 (31.1%)	15 (24.6%)	30 (46.9%)	21 (33.9%) †
HD vintage, months	31 [23; 48]	53 [20; 64]	47 [24; 68] †	45 [23; 73]	31 [15; 48]	40 [17; 69] †
BMI, kg/m ²	26.4 ± 4.4	25.1 ± 4.2	24.7 ± 4.2 *	23.5 ± 4.3	22.4 ± 4.2	21.2 ± 4.5 †
Cinacalcet hydrochloride use	9 (15.3%)	10 (16.9%)	4 (6.6%)	14 (23.0%)	11 (17.2%)	12 (19.4%)
Active vitamin D use	28 (47.5%)	24 (40.7%)	24 (39.3%)	43 (70.5%)	47 (73.4%)	38 (61.3%)
Albumin, g/L	4.32 ± 0.52	4.29 ± 0.59	4.20 ± 0.49	3.81 ± 0.40	3.79 ± 0.29	3.78 ± 0.31
Hemoglobin, g/dL	11.79 ± 1.53	12.19 ± 1.70	11.65 ± 1.52	10.39 ± 0.85	10.34 ± 1.22	10.08 ± 0.84
Total calcium, mg/dL	9.15 ± 0.74	9.15 ± 0.77	9.08 ± 0.69	9.00 ± 0.81	8.74 ± 0.61	9.15 ± 0.88 †
Calcium corr., mg/dL	8.83 ± 0.75	8.86 ± 0.91	8.88 ± 0.86	9.25 ± 0.74	8.98 ± 0.55	9.41 ± 0.78 †
Phosphate, mg/dL	4.84 ± 1.31	4.23 ± 1.14	3.84 ± 1.19 †	5.12 ± 1.04	4.93 ± 1.05	4.76 ± 1.03
wPTH, ρg/mL	256 [217; 354]	157 [115; 229]	76 [39; 135] †	188 [136; 237]	108 [70; 150]	52 [29; 83] †
iPTH, ρg/mL	479 [356; 611]	257 [188; 378]	110 [50; 200] †	284 [219; 393]	159 [109; 225]	70 [41; 115] †
Total ALP, xUNL	0.65 [0.51; 0.82]	0.69 [0.53; 0.93]	0.71 [0.53; 1.08] †	0.77 [0.59; 0.90]	0.82 [0.63; 1.07]	0.96 [0.70; 1.37] †
BALP, μg/L	21.4 [14.2; 32.0]	24.9 [17.1; 35.6]	27.2 [15.6; 51.1] *	14.2 [11.4; 19.3]	16.8 [11.8; 22.7]	16.9 [12.2; 25.2]
TRAP5b, U/L	5.84 [4.44; 6.93]	5.59 [3.98; 8.85]	5.46 [3.54; 7.90]	3.47 [2.39; 4.47]	3.73 [2.29; 5.19]	3.19 [2.27; 4.32]

Data are mean±SD, median[IQR], or n(%) with †=p<0.05 and *=p<0.10 by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), Kruskal-Wallis equality-of-populations rank test, or Pearson's X² test, respectively

Abbr.: ALP=alkaline phosphatase, BALP=bone-specific alkaline phosphatase, iPTH=intact parathyroid hormone, TRAP5b=tartrate resistant acid phosphatase isoform 5b, wPTH=whole parathyroid hormone, xUNL=times upper normal limit of the assay

Suppl Table 2 Determinants of skeletal parathyroid hormone responsiveness in Belgian and Japanese patients **excluding patients with a previous parathyroidectomy**

	Ln (TRAP5b/iPTH) ratio			Ln (BALP/iPTH) ratio			Ln (ALP/iPTH) ratio		
	Model adjusted R ² 14%			Model adjusted R ² 13%			Model adjusted R ² 9%		
	β	SE	<i>p</i>	β	SE	<i>p</i>	β	SE	<i>p</i>
Nationality, Japanese	-0.082	0.087	0.35	0.096	0.094	0.31	0.157	0.098	0.11
Age, yrs	0.002	0.003	0.57	0.002	0.003	0.53	-0.000	0.003	0.93
Sex, male	-0.167	0.077	0.03	-0.194	0.083	0.02	-0.168	0.087	0.05
BMI, kg/m ²	-0.051	0.009	<0.001	-0.037	0.009	<0.001	-0.022	0.010	0.03
HD vintage, mo	0.000	0.001	0.82	0.001	0.001	0.69	-0.001	0.001	0.29
Diabetes mellitus	0.240	0.076	0.002	0.280	0.082	0.001	0.237	0.086	0.006
Albumin, g/dL	-0.111	0.082	0.18	-0.073	0.090	0.42	-0.163	0.093	0.08
Phosphate, mg/dL	-0.061	0.030	0.04	-0.118	0.032	<0.001	-0.074	0.034	0.03
Calcium, mg/dL	0.076	0.049	0.12	0.050	0.053	0.35	0.122	0.056	0.03
Active vitamin D use	-0.088	0.072	0.22	-0.083	0.078	0.29	-0.142	0.082	0.08
Calcimimetic use	0.102	0.097	0.29	-0.007	0.106	0.95	-0.055	0.110	0.62

Data are linear regression β -values, with standard errors (SE) and *p*-values

Abbr.: ALP=alkaline phosphatase, BALP=bone-specific alkaline phosphatase, BMI=body mass index, HD=hemodialysis, iPTH=intact parathyroid hormone, TRAP5b=tartrate resistant acid phosphatase isoform 5b

Suppl Figure 1 Levels of bone-specific alkaline phosphatase (BALP) and tartrate resistant acid phosphatase type 5b (TRAP5b) across quartiles of intact parathyroid hormone (PTH) levels; *p* by Wilcoxon ranksum test between Belgian and Japanese in each quartile

Suppl Figure 2 The relationship between total alkaline phosphatase (ALP) over intact parathyroid hormone (PTH), both expressed as times upper normal limit (UNL)

Suppl Figure 3 Levels of tartrate resistant acid phosphatase type 5b (TRAP5b) across quartiles of intact parathyroid hormone (PTH) levels in patients **not** receiving active vitamin D

